

Assessment of Integrating Injury Prevention Topics into Primary Education

Ugochi Obidiegwu, Victoria Etuk. October 2022

Abstract

Unintentional injury is the leading cause of death in children below 14. This study aimed to demonstrate the effects of a regular safety education program on the knowledge levels of children in primary 4, 5, and 6 leveraging creative expressions. The study used a self-designed survey to collect data from a range of participants obtained through a convenience sampling method to derive results. The research showed that after a defined timeframe, the learner's safety knowledge level increased, and they were able to share new knowledge with others by leveraging different creative expressions. This research project was set in a summer camp project implemented by Dolly Children Foundation in Magboro, Ogun State, Nigeria. Before the children were taught, knowledge levels were assessed through a pre-test. They were trained for four weeks and were assessed again through a post-training test. They also got a chance to make creative group presentations based on their new knowledge. This research demonstrates that when children are taught about safety in a creative and systematic manner, it increases their knowledge base, and they are able to pass on that knowledge to people within their spheres of influence. Based on these findings, we recommend that a wider range of injury prevention topics should be added to the existing education curriculum, creative instructional materials should be provided to each child for personal learning, and a regularly scheduled time for weekly safety education for learners in schools should be implemented.

Introduction

According to the International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, “an estimated 644,855 children under the age of 15 were killed by an injury, and between 10 million and 30 million more suffered a non-fatal injury”.¹ To increase and improve child safety knowledge, a new curriculum was implemented in 2014 in Nigeria. This curriculum had a new subject, Religion and National Values, which has four major components, one of which is Security Education. Security Education mostly covers areas of security broadly, and injury prevention is only referenced in a few themes in another component, Social Studies.² Additionally, there are varied implementation levels on the teaching of this subject aspect across different states in Nigeria. This should not be as effective implementation of curriculum improvements across the country hinges on adequate qualified teachers and adequate instructional materials on the subject.³ Therefore, the Train Them Young Initiative (#2TYI) research project in Magboro, Ogun State, Nigeria, was aimed at demonstrating and measuring the increase in injury prevention knowledge in learners when safety education training and instructional materials are provided within timed intervals.

Hypotheses

If learners are taught about different safety topics regularly over a defined period, then they will know how to stay safe and reduce unintentional injury. If learners are taught

¹ Sleet, D. A. (2018). The Global Challenge of Child Injury Prevention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9): 1921. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6163498/>

² Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council. (2015). eCurriculum. Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council. <https://nerdc.org.ng/eCurriculum/SubjectGroups.aspx?SubEducationLevelId=1&SubjectGroupId=5>

³ Otaru, B. M. (2015). The Role of Teachers in the Implementation of the Revised 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum on Religion and National Values in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*. Vol. 1 No.8 <https://iiardpub.org/get/IJEE/VOL%201/105-112.pdf>

about safety using creative expressions, then they can do the same and share their new knowledge with others.

Literature Review

According to the Center for Disease Control (CDC), the leading cause of death in children aged 14 and below are accidents (unintentional injuries).⁴ According to the International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, a large proportion of these unintentional injuries (for example, burns, suffocation, poisoning, and falls) occurred in or around the home while others occurred in the community (for example, transportation-related injuries, drowning, and sports injuries). These injuries represent a serious burden to the injured person and their family. It represents a tremendous economic and community burden, yet, most are predictable and preventable.⁵ According to the World Health Organization, up to 50% of young children with unintentional injuries who present to a hospital are left with some form of disability.⁶ Deaths from injuries are projected to increase from 5.1 million to 8.4 million (9.2% of all global deaths), and injuries are estimated to be the third leading cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) by the year 2020.⁷ These data show the depth of this issue and the reason we must consider proactive solutions.

⁴ CDC FastStats <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/fastats/child-health.htm>

⁵ Sleet, D. A. (2018). The Global Challenge of Child Injury Prevention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9): 1921. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6163498/>

⁶ Aruna Chandran, Adnan A. Hyder, Corinne Peek-Asa, The Global Burden of Unintentional Injuries and an Agenda for Progress, *Epidemiologic Reviews*, Volume 32, Issue 1, April 2010, Pages 110–120, <https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxq009>

⁷ Fatmi, Z., Hadden, W.C., Razzak, J.A. *et al.* Incidence, patterns and severity of reported unintentional injuries in Pakistan for persons five years and older: results of the National Health Survey of Pakistan 1990–94. *BMC Public Health* 7, 152 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-7-152>

While the initial thought might be that parents should be more intentional about protecting their children, research by Younesian et al. (2016) states some of the contributing factors to these rates of unintentional injuries. According to their research, the most important risk factors reported for home injury include living in unsafe homes, low socioeconomic status, and mothers' low knowledge and inappropriate attitudes. A study performed in 14 European countries has shown that the most important obstacle to adopting preventive measures is the inability of mothers to take continuous care of their children, followed by poor knowledge about factors involved in injuries.⁸ This means that programs targeted at only parents are not enough because what happens when the parents cannot be reached? Reducing preventable injury requires a multi-stakeholder approach. Equipping the children themselves through a structured learning program over a timed duration can be an effective addition to the injury prevention approach. The children learn for themselves and can also teach others within their spheres of influence, like their peers and parents.⁹ This research project builds on the existing body of work by implementing one of the recurring recommendations on injury prevention - education programs for learners.¹⁰

⁸ Younesian S, Mahfoozpour S, Ghafari Shad E et al.: Unintentional Home Injury Prevention in Preschool Children; a Study of Contributing Factors. *Emergency* (2016); 4(2): 72-77
<https://journals.sbmu.ac.ir/index.php/emergency/article/view/9617/7408>

⁹ Train Them Young Initiative (#2TYI), Magboro. 2022 [Train Them Young Initiative \(#2TYI\) in Magboro](#)

¹⁰ Sleet, D. A. (2018). The Global Challenge of Child Injury Prevention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9): 1921. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6163498/>

Methods

The research used the convenience sampling method because the participants were available and willing to participate in the study. Two hundred children in the Dolly Children Foundation summer camp who are in primary 4, 5, and 6 were the participants of this study. Due to limited funding, it was more cost-effective to work with a particular child education center than work with several child education centers.

The study leveraged both qualitative and quantitative methods. The study used pre-training and post-training surveys to generate quantitative data. It assessed group presentations and used interviews to generate qualitative data. Two hundred learners participated at the beginning of the program. The duration was four weeks. During this intervention, there were two major observations to be made:

1. Was there an increase in access to injury prevention topics for the learners?
2. Was there an increase in knowledge due to the provision of age-appropriate child safety education resources within a timed interval?

For the post-test, the minimum score to qualify for an increase in knowledge was 15 out of 20. For the group presentation, there were two major criteria to be considered: effective safety knowledge dissemination and creativity.

The study population was learners - male and female – in primary 4, 5, and 6. These children were chosen instead of the entire summer camp because, at this class level, they had the ability to read the provided child safety storybook, *The Adventures of Muna*. The study began in the first week of August 2022 and ended in the last week of August 2022.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents: Of the 82 learners with complete test scores, the mean age was 11.08 ± 1.55 years with a range of 8 years. Females comprised 58% of participants. The mean age of females was 10.9 ± 1.48 years, and the mean age of males was 11.3 ± 1.66 years.

Figure 1: Sex distribution of children

Pre-test Scores: Pre-test scores ranged from 5 points to 20, giving a range of 15. The mean pre-test score was 14.49 ± 3.43 points. The mean score of females (14.95 points) was higher than males (13.85 points); however, this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.1550$).

Figure 2: Table of pre-test scores

Group	Observations	Mean	Std err	Std dev	[95% conf. interval]		T statistic	p-value
Female	47	14.95745	0.4202962	2.881406	14.11143	15.80346	1.4359	0.1550
Male	34	13.85294	0.693916	4.046191	12.44116	15.26472		

Figure 3: Distribution of pre-test scores

Post-test scores: Post-test scores had a similar range to pre-test scores, ranging from 5 points to 20. The mean post-test score was 16.09 ± 3.0 points. The mean score of females (16.36 points) was higher than males (15.74 points). However, this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.3560$).

Figure 4: Distribution of post-test-scores

Figure 5: Distribution of post-test scores by gender

Group	Observations	Mean	Std err	Std dev	[95% conf. interval]		T statistic	p-value
Female	47	16.3617	.3779608	2.591168	15.60091	17.1225	0.928	0.3560
Male	34	15.73529	.5975422	3.48424	14.51959	16.951		

Effect of safety training

Overall, there was a 130-point difference between the total post-test score (1304) and the total pre-test scores (1174). The total post-test score was 130 points higher than the total pre-test scores. About half of the participants (47, 58.02%) exhibited good knowledge of safety (greater than or equal to 15 points) on the pre-test. However, this number increased to 62 (76.5%) on the post-test.

Discussions

The focus of this research was to measure the increase in knowledge levels when learners were provided with safety education resources in a consistent manner over a timed duration. According to data generated, safety knowledge levels moved from 58.02% at the beginning to 76.5% in the written tests at the end of the research. In addition, the learners were able to leverage creative methods like songs, drama, speeches, and cardboard presentations to share their new knowledge with peers in the last week of the project.¹¹

According to collected data, females were younger than their male colleagues, but they scored higher. This might mean that females are informed early on safety issues because of their susceptibility to these risks. It might also mean that they tend to be more safety conscious than their male peers. Furthermore, these results were achieved within just one month. In a longer timeline, like an academic term or academic year, the results have the potential to be even more profound.

However, there were limitations to this study. At the beginning of the study, there were 200 participants at the free summer camp, but only 82 got to the last week of the study. According to the implementing partner, Dolly Children Foundation, some of the learners could no longer attend the free summer camp due to family responsibilities and circumstances beyond their control. To build on this study, an education intervention like this research project should be replicated with larger learner numbers and run over the course of an academic year.

¹¹ Train Them Young Initiative (#2TYI), Magboro. 2022 [Train Them Young Initiative \(#2TYI\) in Magboro](#)

Recommendations

In order to systematically train learners to be safety conscious, these recommendations are important:

1. A wider variety of topics on injury prevention should be added under the Security Education and Social Studies component in order to adequately equip learners.¹²
2. A regularly scheduled time for weekly safety education for learners should be implemented in schools.
3. There should be the provision of relevant age-appropriate instructional materials to learners to support personal learning.
4. There should also be adequate teacher preparedness and provision of instructional materials so that the teachers have resources to work with.¹³

These recommendations are effective as an increase in knowledge levels can be measured at the end of the academic year. It is administratively feasible because there is an existing Basic Education Curriculum, only an update is required. It is also socially acceptable as stakeholders can clearly see how this improves outcomes for learners in schools. These courses of action are relevant because they will deliver more knowledgeable and safety-conscious children and, by extension lead to a reduction in preventable accidents affecting children.

¹² Sleet, D. A. (2018). The Global Challenge of Child Injury Prevention. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9): 1921. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6163498/>

¹³ Gbadamosi, T. V. Ajayi, O. A (2018). Assessment of Social Studies Theme in Context of Secondary School Religion and National Values Curriculum in Ibadan Metropolis. *Nigerian Journal of Social Work* Vol 17: 149 -162
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343190129_Assessment_of_Implementation_Of_Social_Studies_Theme_In_Context_Of_Secondary_School_Religion_and_National_Values_Curriculum_In_Ibadan_Metropolis

Obidiegwu,U. (2017). The Adventures of Muna.
<https://www.amazon.com/Adventures-Muna-Special-safety-guide/dp/9789625219>

Disclosures

Consent was obtained from all participants and their caregivers in this project.